

AN EFFECTIVE METHOD OF DEVELOPING BUSINESS CASE STUDIES BASED ON COMPANY ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

Many business schools have adopted case method in management research and in teaching pedagogy with the belief that it is a most powerful way to study and learn new lessons required to identify, understand, and solve the problems in the process of managing and leading the organizations. Analysing business cases of companies force students to grapple with exactly the kinds of situations, decisions, and dilemmas managers confront every day. A good business case will include the problem, identify all the possible options to solve the problem, and provides adequate information along with uncertainties to the decision-makers to choose which course of action will be best for the organisation. Case analysis is a participatory method in which the students play a lead role in their own and each other's learning. The instructors moderate the discussions ask questions, monitors the dialogue, supports debate, and records the frameworks used for analysing situations, concepts, models, strategies used in the problem of the system/organization to engage students in a decision-making process of a challenging, interactive learning environment. Both types of cases can be analysed in a classroom set-up provided the instructor finds them as appropriate for the topic and subject under discussion. Company analysis is a powerful tool in developing both research case study and teaching case study in business management subject. In this paper, we have discussed the case studies based on company analysis, case studies published by top publishers on company analysis, difference between research case study and teaching case study, company analysis as a methodology in management research, an effective method of developing research case studies based on company analysis using a framework for research case study based on company analysis, and the possible recommendations based on analysis.

Index Terms: Business Case Development, Case Study as Pedagogy, Case Study as Research, Various Analysis Techniques in Case Study & Company Analysis

1. Introduction:

Business case studies are used to study the business model/issues of a firm systematically by identifying either research oriented issues and analysing them to create new knowledge or to learn a better way of solving the problems related to such issues. Accordingly, business case studies are used both in explorative research as a qualitative research method and teaching methods as teaching-learning pedagogy. The objective of research oriented case studies is to study and analyse a system to see new information to provide recommendations to expand the system or improve the performance of the system. The objective of teaching case studies is to learn the system for identifying the problems and to find optimum solutions to such problems using theoretical concepts. The objective of research case studies may vary depending on subjects like medicine, engineering, social science and business management. Research based case studies in business management may focus on analysing a single issue or many issues of an organization or an industry. These issues may relate to various aspects of the business and its environment. Even though the research case study is considered as a qualitative research method, many case studies collect large masses of quantitative data like performance data, profitability data, employment data, marketing data, etc. for a specific organisation. Research based case studies provide suggestions or recommendations to improve the system whereas teaching case studies pose some questions for the reader to analyse and recommend the solution. Many business schools have adopted case method in management teaching due to the belief that it is a most powerful way to learn new skills required to identify, understand, and solve the problems to manage and lead the organizations. Analysing business cases of the companies force students to grapple with exactly the kinds of situations, decisions and dilemmas managers confront every day. A good business case will include the problem, identify all the possible options to solve the problem, and provides adequate information along with uncertainties to the decision-makers to choose which course of action will be best for the organisation. Teaching case method is a participatory method in which the students play a lead role in their own and each other's learning. The instructors moderate the discussions ask questions, monitors the dialogue, supports debate, and records the frameworks used for analysing situations, concepts, models, strategies used in the problem of the system/organization to engage students in a decision-making process of a challenging, interactive learning environment. Company analysis based on a systematic procedure and objective can be used as a research based case study or teaching based case study. It is easy to develop both research case studies and teaching case studies compared to empirical research in many cases so that the students studying in higher education courses can develop case studies based on company analysis as a

part of their research project provided they collect In this paper, we have discussed the case studies based on company analysis, difference between research case study and teaching case study, company analysis as a methodology in management research, an effective method of developing research case studies based on company analysis using a framework for research case study based on company analysis, and the possible recommendations based on analysis [1-9].

2. Case Studies Based on Company Analysis:

The various business issues of a company or group of companies can be analysed by means of internal and external factors affected the decisions of the managers related to the problems such as to fulfil the objectives, to effective usage of resources, improve the product/service, improve various business processes, improve the business performance, business sustainability, business expansion, technology aspects, competition, collaboration, companies financial decisions, recruitment and training decisions, strategic planning, tactical decisions, control decisions, operations decisions, research & development issues, new products/services, issues related to stakeholders such management, employees, suppliers, customers, collaborators, government, and the society. The case study in company analysis may also focus on various strategies used by the company for facing completion, to become a monopoly, for survival, and for sustainability for a long time with profit. The company performance based on company executive's decision can be correlated with various theories of organizational behaviour and performance. Sometimes the company's poor business performance leading to bankruptcy can be analysed and the reason for such failure can be identified.

Table 1: Some of the HBP/IVEY business case studies published during 2016 related to company analysis as an example.

S.No	Business Case	Publisher	Issue
1	i-flex solutions limited (B): The Oracle Years	HBR	Growth saga
2	i-flex solutions limited (A): Winning Unconventionally	HBR	Survival strategy with limited resources
3	Ranbaxy Laboratories Limited: Changing Aspirations	HBR	Business expansion
4	3D Printing at Imaginarium If you can think it, we can build it	HBR	Innovation in technology
5	Leading The Tata Group (B): The Cyrus Mistry Years	HBR	Leadership
6	Leading The Tata Group (A): The Ratan Tata Years	HBR	Leadership
7	Ace Designers – Competing through Process Improvement	HBR	Improving business Process
8	Aravind Eye Care's Vision Centers – Reaching out to the Rural Poor	HBR	Philanthropy based expansion
9	Fullerton: Risk Analytics and Business Strategy	IIM-B	Decision with Risk
10	LP Laboratories Ltd.: Financing Working Capital	IIM-B	Investment decision
11	Fraud Analytics at MCA Technology Solutions – Predicting Earnings Manipulations by Indian Firms	IIM-B	Innovation in prediction analytics model
12	DDB Mudra Group: Profitable Growth	IIM-B	Growth strategy
13	DDB Mudra Group: Transformative Growth	IIM-B	Transformation strategy
14	Maxim in India (A)	IIM-B	Marketing strategy
15	Customer Analytics at Flipkart.Com	IIM-B	Customer value creation
16	Bühler India – Assessing Growth Opportunities	IIM-B	Brand extension and marketing strategy
17	Bajaj RE60: The Branding Challenge of Disruptive Innovation	IVEY	Business Challenges
18	Amul's IT-Enabled Service Delivery to Dairy Farmers	IVEY	IT Innovation
19	Café Coffee Day: Brand Transformation through Repositioning	IVEY	Repositioning of Products/Services
20	Castrol India Limited: An Innovative Distribution Channel	IVEY	Business Innovation
21	HCL Technologies: Pushing the Billion-Dollar Website	IVEY	ICT Innovation
22	Hubtown (A): Designing a Bottom-Up	IVEY	Business Innovation

	Approach to Performance Management		
23	<u>Alchemist Hospital</u>	IIM-A	Service quality
24	Shivani Carriers Pvt Ltd: Managing Employee Motivation at the Bottom of the Pyramid	IIM-A	HR Strategy
25	JSW Steel's Ispat Acquisition: The Turnaround Strategy	IIM-A	Acquisition based turnaround strategy
26	Dadri Power Plant of National Thermal Power Corporation Limited	IIM-A	Innovations in Project
27	Suzlon Energy	IIM-A	Business Strategy
28	Nestlé: Nutrition, Health, and Wellness	HBS	Product Innovation
29	BASF: Co-Creating Innovation (A)	HBS	Innovation & Sustainability
30	Tesla in 2015	HBS	Business strategy
31	Blue Sky: Investing in Water	HBS	Investment decision
32	Deutsche Bank: Structured Retail Products	HBS	New product
33	Reinventing Best Buy	HBS	Turnaround Strategy

Table 2: Some of the HBP/IVEY business case studies published during 2016 related to Industry analysis as an example.

S.No	Business Case	Publisher	Industry
1	Indian Software Services Industry the Changing Landscape	HBR	Software
2	Markdown Optimization for an Indian Apparel Retailer	HBR	Apparel Industry
3	Note on the Canadian Transportation Industry	Ivey	Transportation
4	Involuntary Attrition in Indian Information Technology Firms (A)	IIM-A	Information Technology
5	Growth Strategies in the Pharmaceutical Industry	HBR	Pharmaceuticals
6	The Canadian Television Industry Confronts Subscription Video on Demand	Ivey	Television Industry
7	Using the SWOT Framework in the Healthcare Sector	Ivey	Healthcare Industry
8	The Global Oil and Gas Industry	Thunderbird	Oil & Gas Industry

Table 3: No. of Business Case Studies published by World top Publishers during last 3 years.

S.No	Publisher	No. of cases during 2013	No. of cases during 2014	No. of cases during 2015	No. of cases during 2016
1	Darden Business Publishing	112	127	76	92
2	Ivey Publishing	263	307	287	415
3	Harvard Business Publishing	811	739	649	588
4	INSEAD Case Publishing	-	-	-	103
5	Kellogg	17	30	22	21
6	Thunderbird, USA	23	12	14	19
7	SDA Bocconi, Italy	15	19	13	14
8	IIM-B	24	12	25	28
9	IIM-A	25	20	22	27
10	ISB, India	49	36	34	26
11	Nanyang, Singapore.	13	10	06	09

3. Difference Between Research Case Study & Teaching Case Study:

Research case studies based on company analysis are usually focus on identifying some issues related to specified objectives through empirical enquiries. This method of the case study is useful for trying to test theoretical models by using them in real world situations. The case study based research method is different from the statistical method that its results cannot be extrapolated to fit an entire question of the study. But it is argued that a case study provides more realistic responses than a purely statistical survey. By including both quantitative and qualitative data, case study method helps to explain both the process and outcome of an issue or a phenomenon through complete observation, reconstruction and analysis of the company under investigation [10]. Other than business management research, the case study method is used extensively in the fields of Sociology, Law, Medicine, government, and in education [11]. Out of different categories of case studies, the major three categories of case studies are exploratory, descriptive and explanatory case studies [12]. The exploratory case studies develop to explore any issue in the data which serves as a point of interest to the researcher. The descriptive case studies set to describe the natural phenomena which occur within the data in question. The explanatory case studies check the data closely both at a surface and deep level in order to understand the phenomena in the data. Another class of case study category includes interpretive and evaluative

case studies [13]. Through interpretive case studies, the researcher aims to interpret the data by developing conceptual categories, challenging or supporting the assumptions made related to them. In evaluative case studies, the researcher analyse and adds their judgment to the issues found in the data. On the other hand, a teaching case study is mainly developed to learn the practical implications of theories in real world phenomenon in the social or business systems. The major difference between research case studies and teaching case studies are listed in table 4.

Table 4: Difference between research case study and teaching case study on a Company

S.No	Research Case Study	Teaching Case Study
1	An effective research case study on a company identifies important issues related to organizational, business, or industry problems and the manager's decision on success/failure in identifying an optimum solution to such problems.	An effective teaching case study can have attributes like ambiguity, conflict between issues or people, leaves important issues unresolved, complex to allow multiple levels of analysis, introduces a tension between alternative courses of action, ends with more questions than answers, forces a decision.
2	An effective research case study on a company should contain background information about the company, area of interest, analysis of specific issue/problem, identifying optimum solution from alternatives, or issues which have changed the fate of the company positively or negatively, and some of the exhibit materials supporting the analysis.	An effective teaching case study should contain background information about the issue, analysis of that identified issue, hint to identify the problem, exhibit materials to analyse the issues, set of questions to fix the problem and apply various management theories while suggesting optimum decisions to solve the problems.
3	Research case study is usually developed by P.G. or research course students	Teaching case is usually developed by teachers to add experiential learning feature to classroom teaching/learning.
4	A company analysis case study should contain the company name as central with or without identified issue as the case name.	A teaching case should contain the issue/problem as central along with or without the name of the company.
5	Good company analysis provides crucial information about the company, its operation, strategy, problems faced and how it solved problems through decision making. It also discusses efforts of the company on success or failure of achieving its objectives	Good teaching cases enable students to put themselves in the shoes of actual managers to learn about decision-making. The students analyze situations, develop alternatives, choose plans of action and implementation, and communicate and defend their findings.
6	Research cases focus on learning the company business, products/services, strategy, struggle, and environment systematically to create new knowledge, insight, or wisdom.	Teaching Cases are used to test students' understanding of theory, to connect theory with application, and to develop practical insight, or wisdom.
7	Company business analysis and hence multi-problems analysis	Specific issue-based analysis and hence usually single problem analysis
8	Usually need more theories, models, and frameworks of business management subject including all functional areas of the company business.	Since the teaching case is specific issue focussed, relative less theories, models, and frameworks are used for problems identification and analysis.
9	Research case studies usually conclude with recommendations	Teaching case studies usually conclude with
10	In research case studies, the researcher initially collects the qualitative information about the industry where the company is a part. Then he has to collect company information both internal and external quantitatively by means of either through exploratory method or empirical method to find the relationship between various decision variables and develop recommendations for optimum decisions to identified problem or the gap between the present state of affair and expected future state of affairs.	Teaching cases force readers to draw threads of information together and rigorously apply analysis. The three levels of difficulty in the teaching case analysis are (1) Include the problem and the protagonist's solution, and have the students analyze whether it worked. (2) Present the problem, and have students provide a solution or alternatives. (3) Describe the situation, and have students figure out the problem/solution/alternatives.

4. Company Analysis as a Methodology in Management Research:

A researcher who wants to develop a business case of a company in any specified industry sector needs to find answers to following questions.

Step 1: How to choose a company?

Step 2: What to study in a chosen company and its business?

Step 3: How to fix issues/phenomenon?

Step 4: How to identify the problems/situations?

Step 5: How to analyse the problem/situation?

Step 6: How to apply various Business Management Theories & Concepts?

Step 7: What are the analysis techniques suitable?

Step 8: How to provide suggestions/recommendations to improve the performance or solve the problems?

Step 9: How to arrive conclusion?

4.1 How to Choose a Company?: A researcher chooses a company based on his area of interest, the objective of his research, the industry sector he need to focus, the issues to be discussed, the business model to be evaluated, the companies in the nearby location, the functional area or specialization he wants to focus, the management theories he wants to test, the easiness of collecting required data etc. The researcher can choose either local or national or international companies for his analysis. Based on surveying the companies available in a chosen industry functioning in his location where he has accessibility to collect data and information, or by collecting information about the business and strategies from the company website and from various other sites. The researcher can identify the local companies and their business by collecting the information from local chamber of commerce and industries, the associations of the companies and then by refereeing their websites. Companies in a given sector or industry can be selected at country level by referring company ranking surveys conducted by various agencies like Economics Times 500 companies list or any other list where the researcher is able to collect required information about various issues interested in. At global level, many international and multinational companies list can be obtained by Financial Times global 500 companies list, Fortune 500 companies list etc. By using information communication technology and internet, one can get useful information on any company from its and various other websites which can be effectively used to analyse the company.

4.2 What to Study?: Ones the company for analysis is chosen, the researcher has to address what are the issues to be analysed. The issue can be identified by studying the historical performance of the company, the products and services it offers, the company business, the strategy it follows, the issues/phenomenon to be examined, the business model it follows etc. depending on the interest of the researcher or the problem to be discussed. The detailed idea of the topics to be studied based on collected information about the company are given in next section.

4.3 How to Fix Issues/Phenomenon?: After choosing the company the researcher has to collect the information about the performance of the company along with its challenges and opportunities through a pilot study. At this stage, the researcher may find an issue interesting to him based on his objectives/ expectations for further focus. The issue may be related to its production/service processes, accumulation of resources, performances in functional areas, business models and strategies, profit or loss, technology adoption, business innovations, future business opportunities and strategies etc.

4.4 How to Identify the Problem/Situation?: In this stage, the researcher has to identify the problem/problems to be discussed/solved form the issues they have choose related to that company. A problem is a gap between the present state of affairs to future expected state of affairs within environmental/situations restrictions. Sometimes the researcher may have interest and objective of studying a particular aspect of the business of the company, for example, the financial performance of the company and its effect on future business, the expansion strategy of the company through mergers and acquisitions, the business model, the business strategy, etc.

4.5 How to Analyse the Problem/Situation?: Once the problem /situation is identified, the researcher should collect information further to understand and analyse the problem. The problems or situations can be analysed through the collected information and documents related to company business, its environment and competitors, observation of its historical performance, its products/services, its marketing opportunities and strategies, its resources, collaborations, internal strength, ability to manage competitions, sustainability, monopoly business model/ability, survival abilities, stakeholders view point, business factors and critical elements related to business, etc. Various tools, techniques, theories and concepts can be used in this stage of company analysis.

4.6 How to apply various Business Management Theories & Concepts: Depending on the problems /situations /issues, the researcher has to use various analysis techniques, frameworks, tools, or methods to check the appropriateness of theories and concepts in business management. This include general management theories, organizational behaviour theories, methods used in functional areas like marketing concepts & theories, financial analysis, and leadership theories. Based on the observations and analysis of the business performance of a chosen company, the researcher can suggest modifications in the decisions of the company

managers or changes in business models. Sometimes, based on observation, the researcher can suggest modifications in the theoretical frameworks which may lead to birth of new theories.

4.7 What are the Analysis Techniques Suitable?: SWOC analysis framework [14-16] is used to identify the internal factors that influence an organization's performance. It identifies the Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Challenges of the Company for its present and future sustainable business. PESTLE analysis framework [17-18] is a useful method to identify the external factors that influence an organization. It describes the challenges and opportunities of the company for its sustained business based on Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors. ABCD analysis framework [19-30] is an effective and integrated method for factor and elemental analysis based on different internal and external issues using four constructs namely advantages, benefits, constructs, and disadvantages. Financial analysis discloses the financial health of the company and hence its sustainability and ability on investment on future expansions.

4.8 How to Arrive to Suggestions to Improve the Performance or Solve the Problems?: Once the company business is analysed and various alternative solutions to identified problems are proposed, the researcher has to suggest the optimum solution for the identified problems. At this stage, the researcher can use various optimization techniques, probabilistic theories, online analytical methods, and decision theories to suggest the optimum solution. Various recommendations can be provided to implement the solution, improve the performance or to improve the productivity.

4.9 How to Arrive Conclusion?: This is the final stage in company analysis where the researcher concludes his analysis and fulfils his objective of studying the chosen problem and situation in the company by mentioning the gist of his observations.

5. Framework for Research Case Study based on Company Analysis:

The research case study based on company analysis can have two sections as company industry analysis and company analysis. Usually, the company industry analysis should contain more qualitative discussions and the company analysis should be more quantitative in nature.

5.1 Company Industry Analysis: The fate of the company to a larger extent is tied to overall performance in the industry. In which it finds itself. The given individual company's performance may be better or worse than the industry it belongs as a whole. Understanding the industry or multiple industries where the company competes is essential to develop a baseline for understanding the external conditions and competitions the company is facing currently and in the future. This can be analysed by using Michael Porters' five forces framework. The five forces analysis simplifies an industry's competitive environment and its profitability. The five basic forces are: (1) Bargaining Power of Customers. This affects the profitability of a given industry. The various factors like the ease with which customers can switch to the competitor's products, the price sensitivity of the customers, the volume which buyers command are deciding the bargaining power of customers. (2) Bargaining Power of Suppliers : This includes the concentration of suppliers to an industry compared to the concentration of firms in that industry, the ease of switching away from the industry, the availability of substitute products, the price sensitivity of firms in the industry to input prices, and the ability of suppliers to integrate downwards.(3) Threat of New Entrants : The factors required to face such threat includes high capital investment, a steep long learning curve, high brand equity for existing players, tight government regulation, high switching costs, and constraints in access to resources. (4) Threat of Substitute Products: This depends on factors like buyer switching costs, the similarity features of the substitute product to the reference company product, and the price performance of the substitute product as compared to the reference company product. (5) Intensity of Competitive Rivalry : This depends on the factors like the number and relative size of competitor companies, the industry growth rate in the country, industry exit barriers, whether the industry has high fixed costs or not, and the existence of differentiation between products either in performance or in brand loyalty. Apart from Porter's five forces model, some other factors may also be considered like the impact of Government may either positively or negatively affect the business of the firm. The company's Relationship to its Community may also be a key factor in deciding the profit. The concept like Strategic Alliances in which the competitors or suppliers and customers work together to achieve common goals. This also makes an industry healthier than it otherwise would be or it may be especially beneficial to certain members of the alliance. Along with qualitative industry analysis, doing some quantitative assumptions is also helpful. The five forces framework is particularly useful for making a decision about an industry's profitability. The three major quantitative assumptions used in industry analysis are: industry size, Industry growth rate, and industry profitability. Another important factor which decides the fate of a company in a given industry is the average profit margins, A highly competitive industry is likely to give lower profit margins whereas a less competitive industry will give higher margins. It should be noted that the strong brands may command a higher profit than a weak brand in a given industry and hence one can study why a company may differ from the industry average in profitability.

5.2 Company Analysis: Company analysis include the study of companies business, its internal and external environment, its saga of success or failure, its growth or decline, its stakeholders, their expectations, competitors, collaborators and their strategy, products/service quality analysis, business environment, financial

performance analysis, operational strategy, business strategy, corporate strategy, technology adoption strategy, growth and expansion strategy, marketing strategy, human resource management and retention strategy, business model, leadership and decision making effectiveness, automation and information technology adoption, struggle for sustainability, revenue growth rate, company profitability, research & development, innovation, environmental responsibility, corporate social responsibility, future plan, etc. Depending on the nature of the business, business model, and the size of the company, some of the above factors applicable should be studied to collect relevant data for further analysis. The data related to the above factors can be collected by many sources which include company website, interviews conducted to company personnel, and a questionnaire-based survey conducted on stakeholders, articles published in different magazines and journals, financial statements, annual reports, and any other sources of information. The various components of above factors are listed below.

(1) Business Analysis: Study on business aspects of the company which includes:

- ✓ History of the company
- ✓ Vision, mission, and objectives and of the company
- ✓ Founder, his vision, values, and efforts
- ✓ Business in terms of products and services
- ✓ Growth related decisions
- ✓ Success saga of the company and its business
- ✓ Failures and risk taken as experience
- ✓ Turnaround performance
- ✓ Breakthroughs etc.
- ✓ List of CEO's & their contribution
- ✓ Technology Adoption
- ✓ SWOC & PEST Analysis on the Company and its environment [14-18]

(2) Stakeholder Analysis: Study on the stakeholders of the company which includes:

- ✓ Suppliers/Vendors
- ✓ Customers
- ✓ Investors/shareholders
- ✓ Collaborators
- ✓ After sales support
- ✓ Customers ratings
- ✓ Employees morale & commitment
- ✓ Government Policies etc.

(3) Competitor Analysis: Study on competitors for the company including:

- ✓ List of Major Competitors
- ✓ Their Strategies
- ✓ Their product & services
- ✓ Five Competitive Force Model of Michel Porter [31-32]

(4) Product/Services Quality/Performance Analysis: The quality of the products/services of the company can be analysed using techniques like:

- ✓ ABCD Analysis Framework [19-30]
- ✓ Six sigma quality analysis
- ✓ Quality circle method
- ✓ Customer satisfaction & retention survey

(5) Financial Performance Analysis: Analysing financial statement, Income statement including revenues, cost of goods, cost of Selling, General and Administrative, gross margin, operating margin, net margin etc. are important. The balance sheet of the company can be analysed based on determining the key figures in financial analysis the assets of the company, Liabilities of the company, equity of the company which is the difference between assets and liabilities, debt to equity ratio, net debt/equity ratio to know the company financial risk, return on assets which is net profit divided by total assets, and return on equity which is net profit divided by total equity. Based on financial statement analysis one can determine the following financial ratios:

(i) Profit Ratios

- ✓ Gross profit margin
- ✓ Net profit margin
- ✓ Return on total assets
- ✓ Net income
- ✓ Return on stockholders' equity

(ii) Liquidity Ratios

- ✓ Current ratio
- ✓ Quick ratio

(iii) Activity Ratios

- ✓ Inventory turnover
- ✓ Cost of goods sold
- ✓ Days sales outstanding (DSO)

(iv) Leverage Ratios

- ✓ Debt-to-assets ratio.
- ✓ Total debt
- ✓ Debt-to-equity ratio.
- ✓ Times-covered ratio.

(v) Shareholder-Return Ratios

- ✓ Total shareholder returns
- ✓ Price-earnings ratio
- ✓ Market to book value
- ✓ Dividend yield
- ✓ Market price per share

(vi) Cash Flow: Cash flow statements are usually divided into three sections which show operating, investing and financing cash flow. The operating cash flow is the cash received or paid by a company in a specific time period during its regular business. Operating cash flow items will be usually included in the company's income statement. Investing cash flows are determined by the cash received or cash paid out by the company associated with the investment items. Financing cash flows show the money received or paid out by the company associated with its capitalization and can be related to debt payments or new debt. Another parameter called free cash flow is a figure that is used to show the operating cash generated by a company that is available to be used in a discretionary way. Free cash flow starts from operating cash flow and subtracts those items necessary for the business to be run as an ongoing business entity, called capital expenditures. A detailed and standardized calculation for free cash flow would be net income plus amortization plus depreciation plus the change in cash due to working capital changes less capital expenditure [33].

(vii) Capital Mobilization for Expansion: Capital mobilization ability of the company is the ability of the company in arranging capital which can be money, human capital (labor), raw materials, etc as an expansion investment. Capital mobilization strategies are about how to break down barriers to moving capital. For example, if a country has restrictions about foreign ownership of companies then these restrictions provide a barrier to mobilization of capital into the country. It is also the ability of the company in raise the public money investment for its expansion.

(viii) Company Future Earnings Potential: To forecast a company's earnings in a detailed manner, we should build a financial model which forecasts each item in its income statement. Forecasting each line item would allow us to calculate a net profit figure for future years and this figure would be the company's earnings forecast. One way to do this is to not forecast every line item. By detailed analysis it is possible to forecast revenues, operating margin and non-operating items of a company.

(6) Strategy Analysis: The company analysis case study may include discussion on various strategies adopted and being adopted in order to fulfill the objectives, solve the problems towards maintaining sustainable profit. Some of such strategies to be analyzed are:

- ✓ Various Corporate Strategies
- ✓ Global Strategies
- ✓ Porters Five Competitive Strategies etc.
- ✓ Digital Strategy like usage of information communication technology
- ✓ E-Commerce Strategy to decrease the cost and increase the business share
- ✓ Research & Development Strategy to develop new products, processes, services, business models
- ✓ Marketing Strategy to enhance the demand
- ✓ Customer Retention & New Customer Strategy to expand business
- ✓ Business Expansion Strategies
- ✓ Acquisition & Managing of Human Resource Strategies

(7) Marketing Analysis: Marketing analysis include:

- ✓ Demand for Products & Services
- ✓ Advertisement Strategies
- ✓ Collaboration Strategies
- ✓ Product/service innovation strategies

(8) HR Development & Retention Strategy: The analysis should focus on the ability of the company to attract and retain optimum human resources including:

- ✓ Identification of Human Resources,
- ✓ Recruitment Strategies :
- ✓ Training Strategies :

- ✓ Productivity enhancement strategy
- ✓ Employee motivational strategies
- ✓ Employee replacement strategies

(9) New Technology Adoption Strategy: The analysis should focus on:

- ✓ Inventory of existing technologies
- ✓ Survey of new technology
- ✓ Development of indigenous new technology or procurement of new technology
- ✓ Technology adoption, automation and improving productivity

(10) Leadership Analysis: The company analysis can also include:

- ✓ Leader/Decision Makers
- ✓ Type of leader/leaders
- ✓ Vision of leader
- ✓ Qualities of Leader
- ✓ Futuristic Strategies
- ✓ Acceptance of leader by Organization etc.

(11) Analysis of Implementation of IT and Automation: Quality improvement based on implementation of advanced Information Technology includes:

- ✓ Strategic planning for IT is fundamental to the ultimate effectiveness of IT implementation.
- ✓ Interdepartmental coordination has proven to be a major factor in effective IT implementation.
- ✓ The expertise levels of executives with regard to IT.

(12) Innovation & Future Plan Analysis: More importantly, the company analysis also focuses on the future business strategy of the company and ability of identification of future opportunities. This include [34]:

- ✓ Value added products/services.
- ✓ New product/service development and commercialization.
- ✓ Efforts on customer satisfaction, delight, and retention.
- ✓ Identifying new opportunities etc.

The above thirteen analysis tools provide a researcher to do in-depth study on any company and its ability to carry on its business. In the process of such company analysis, the researcher will learn the company problems, affords and strategies to solve such problems in order to realize its objectives. During such process, the researcher may also find a specific area/issue where expert recommendations or recommendations based on various business/management theories or new models to be suggested. In company case analysis, the researcher can also discuss and find the gap between the characteristics of present business and the ideal conditions and characteristics of such system with the intension to suggest the improvements in the business system [35].

(13) Analysis of Company Business Using Six Thinking Hats Approach: For analysing a given issue or situation, recently introduced six thinking hats technique finds importance due to its ability to identify the attributes of a situation from six different perspectives. In six thinking hats technique, Dr. Edward de Bono outlined different thinking styles required by an individual while analysing a given problem in a systematic way [36]. The technique interrelates different thinking styles used in an effective problem-solving procedure with different coloured hats [37]. This approach guides the individuals to use a particular thinking style represented by individual coloured hat. By conceptualizing each type of hat, the person focuses on the style of thinking associated with each colour. Accordingly, wearing the WHITE hat he adopts Neutral judgements based on facts and figures, wearing the RED hat he will adopt humanistic thinking filled with emotions and feelings, while wearing the YELLOW hat he thinks about the positive aspects of the situation, while wearing the BLACK hat he adopts pessimistic or negative thinking based on comments, criticism, caution & carefulness, while wearing the GREEN hat he adopts creative thinking, while wearing the BLUE hat he adopts thinking based on planning, organizing and controlling [38-39].

6. Recommendations Based on Analysis:

Various recommendations suggested by the researcher towards company business developments through in-depth analysis and discussions are listed below:

- ✓ Recommendations based on organizational objectives
- ✓ Recommendations based on improving organizational efficiency
- ✓ Recommendations based on implementation of suggested solutions
- ✓ Recommendations based on business models
- ✓ Recommendations based on business strategy
- ✓ Recommendations based on accumulation of resources for sustainability
- ✓ Recommendations based on company business expansion
- ✓ Recommendations based on company social responsibilities
- ✓ Recommendations based on technology implementation
- ✓ Recommendations based on financial performance
- ✓ Recommendations based on collaborations and outsourcing

- ✓ Recommendations based on automation
- ✓ Recommendations related to HR policies
- ✓ Recommendations related to marketing strategy
- ✓ Recommendations related to internationalization of production and markets. etc.

7. ABCD Listing on Research Case Study based on Company Analysis:

The predefined condition for ABCD analysis as per its framework is ABCD listing [40-48]. In this section, the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of company analysis are listed.

(1) Advantages of Company Analysis:

- ✓ Studying in and out of the company in terms of its products and services
- ✓ Knowing competitors and their product features
- ✓ Knowing the internal factors and environmental factors affecting the business
- ✓ Knowing the business strategies
- ✓ Study of IT adoption and automation
- ✓ Possibility to calculate the company's future earning potential

(2) Benefits of Company Analysis:

- ✓ Understanding the company business
- ✓ Help to suggest counter strategy for competition
- ✓ Helps to know financial health of the company
- ✓ Will give new insight on the performance of the company and to improve its performance
- ✓ Learning new strategies if any
- ✓ Understanding the benefits of the IT adoption and automation
- ✓ By knowing future earning a potential of the company the investors may get attracted so that the share price may go up.

(3) Constraints of Company Analysis:

- ✓ Collecting required information of chosen company
- ✓ Identifying some internal problems of the company
- ✓ Extracting new knowledge from company analysis
- ✓ In some companies suggesting recommendations for improving performance

(4) Disadvantages of Company Analysis:

- ✓ The company analysis based on internal information disclose company strategy to its competitors.
- ✓ Some companies do not like to hear their weakness/ failures from a third party researcher.
- ✓ By knowing the future earning potential of the company the share price may go down.

8. Conclusions:

Business case writing and publication based on company analysis is one of the strategies of the researchers in many business schools. Adding company analysis in the curriculum for offering credit will enhance the academic involvement in company affairs and hence will improve the amount of industry-institute interaction. In this paper, we have discussed the importance of research-based case studies in business management subject and the publication pattern of such case studies by world top business school publishers on various issues of company analysis for the year 2016 is discussed. The comparison between the structure of research based business case study and teaching business case study on a company is made and a systematic procedure of company analysis is developed as a methodology in management research. Further, a framework for research case study based on company analysis is proposed. Various recommendations to be suggested to the company based on company analysis by the researcher is also outlined and finally, a listing of advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of company analysis as a research model. A more detailed model of writing a business case of different types based on specific issues like (1) Starting new business based on innovative idea, (2) Cases on organizational and business strategies, (3) Cases on functional areas, (4) Cases on technology management, (5) Cases on any management problem at any organizational level, (6) Cases on small business etc. is in progress and will be published in next paper. The model contains how to choose a right issue to develop teaching business case, how to plan the structure, how to develop the business case systematically by collecting the information and by including real-world problem, etc. The model contains the steps of developing, drafting, and publishing both research and teaching business cases in a simple systematic way and also the procedure of developing teaching note to help the instructor while analysing the business case inside the class.

9. References:

1. Fidel, R. (1984). The case study method: a case study. *Library and Information Science Research*, 6(3), 273-288.
2. Yin, R. K. (1992). The case study method as a tool for doing evaluation. *Current Sociology*, 40(1), 121-137.
3. Stake, R. E. (1978). The Case Study Method in Social Inquiry 1. *Educational researcher*, 7(2), 5-8.

4. Stake, R. E. (1983). The case study method in social inquiry. In Evaluation models (pp. 279-286). Springer Netherlands.
5. Flyvbjerg, B. (2006). Five misunderstandings about case-study research. *Qualitative inquiry*, 12(2), 219-245.
6. Gerring, J. (2004). What is a case study and what is it good for?. *American political science review*, 98(02), 341-354.
7. Runeson, P., & Höst, M. (2009). Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering. *Empirical software engineering*, 14(2), 131.
8. Bowen, G. A. (2009). Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative research journal*, 9(2), 27-40.
9. Noor, K. B. M. (2008). Case study: A strategic research methodology. *American journal of applied sciences*, 5(11), 1602-1604.
10. Tellis, Winston, (1997). Introduction to Case Study. *The Qualitative Report*, Volume 3, Number 2, July. (<http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR3-2/tellis1.html>).
11. Zaidah Zainal (2007). Case study as a research method, *Jurnal Kemanusiaan bil.9*, 1-6.
12. Yin, R.K., (1984). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. Beverly Hills, Calif: Sage Publications.
13. McDonough, J. and McDonough, S., (1997). *Research Methods for English Language Teachers*. London: Arnold.
14. Lee S. F., and Ko, A. S. O., (2000"a") Building Balanced Scorecard with SWOT Analysis, and Implementing, Sun Tzu's The Art of Business Management Strategies' on QFD Methodology. *Managerial Auditing Journal* 15 (1-2) pp 68-76.
15. Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.
16. Weihrich, H. (1982). The TOWS matrix—A tool for situational analysis. *Long range planning*, 15(2), 54-66.
17. Maliki, A. B., Jahrin, M. E. B., Kamarulzaman, N. S. B., Ali, N. B. M., Azhar, N. I. B. M., & Chew, B. C. (2012). PESTLE analysis on Bieichi technology—technology which turns plastic waste into fuels.
18. Ho, J. K. K. (2014). Formulation of a systemic PEST analysis for strategic analysis. *European academic research*, 2(5), 6478-6492.
19. Aithal, P. S., (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, business strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems, *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>
20. Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V.T., & Suresh Kumar, P.M. (2015). A New ABCD Technique to Analyze Business Models & Concepts, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(4), 409 – 423. DOI :<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61652>.
21. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V. T., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Application of ABCD Analysis Model for Black Ocean Strategy, *International Journal of Applied Research (IJAR)*, 1(10), 331 - 337. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163424>.
22. Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models. *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business Management*, 3(3), 121 - 130, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.61640.
23. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V. T., & Suresh Kumar P. M. (2016). ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 11-24. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.154233>.
24. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P. M. (2016). Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 30-44, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.154272>.
25. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V. T., & Suresh Kumar P. M. (2016). Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 5(4), 159-170. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161111>.
26. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V. T., & Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016). The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 389-402. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161077>.
27. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, & Aithal P. S., (2016), ABCD analysis of Dye doped Polymers for Photonic Applications, *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 358-378. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.155103>.
28. Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). CCE Approach through ABCD Analysis of 'Theory A' on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(2), 169-185. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164704>.

29. Varun Shenoy, & Aithal P. S., (2016). ABCD Analysis of On-line Campus Placement Model, IRA International Journal of Management & Social Sciences, 5(2), 227-244. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v5.n2.p3>.
30. Aithal, P. S., Shailashree V. T & Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016). Analysis of ABC Model of Annual Research Productivity using ABCD Framework. International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), 1(1), 846-858. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62022>.
31. Porter, M. E. (1985), Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance. New York: The Free Press.
32. Porter, M.E. (2008). The Five Competitive Forces That Shape Strategy. Harvard Business Review. Available at: <http://hbr.org/2008/01/the-five-competitive-forces-that-shape-strategy>.
33. Drake, P. P., & Fabozzi, F. J. (2010). Cash-Flow Analysis. Handbook of Finance.
34. Beaumaster, S. (1999). Information Technology Implementation Issues: An Analysis. <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/handle/10919/27177>. Referred on 07/03/2017.
35. Aithal, P. S. (2015). Concept of Ideal Business & its Realization Using E-Business Model. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), 4(3), 1267–1274. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61648>.
36. De Bono, E. (1999) Six Thinking Hats, Back Bay Books, New York.
37. Govind Sharma, Six Hats Thinking, its analysis and practically used example, <http://blog.simplycareer.net/2013/05/six-hats-thinking-its-analysis-and.html>.
38. Aithal, P. S., Shailashree V. T. & Suresh Kumar P.M. (2016). Factors & Elemental Analysis of Six Thinking Hats Technique using ABCD Framework. International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET), 1(1), 85-95. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.240259>.
39. Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Using Six Thinking Hats as a Tool for Lateral Thinking in Organizational Problem Solving. International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), 1(2), 225-234. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.198724>.
40. Reshma, Aithal P. S., Shailashree V T, Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). An Empirical study on working from home – A popular E-business model, International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research, 2(2), 12-18. DOI :<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164429>.
41. Aithal, P. S., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Theory A for Optimizing Human Productivity, IRA International Journal of Management & Social Sciences, 4(3), 526-535. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v4.n3.p2>.
42. Reshma, Aithal, P. S & Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). Relevance of On-line Office Administration through Working from Home in Future Education System. International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management, 4(4), 44 – 53. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163882>.
43. Padmanabha Shenoy, and Aithal P. S., (2016). A Study on History of Paper and possible Paper Free World. International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), 6(1), 337-355. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161141>.
44. Aithal, P.S., (2015). Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities – A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University. International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR), 4(12), 106-122. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163884>.
45. Aithal P. S., and Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016). Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education. International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), 1(1), 278-284. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161046>.
46. Varun Shenoy and Aithal, P. S. (2016). Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model. International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), 1(1), 766 – 776. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160966>.
47. Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). A New Model for Commercialization of Nanotechnology Products and Services. International Journal of Computational Research and Development, 1(1), 84-93. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163536>.
48. Shubrajyotsna Aithal & Aithal, P. S., (2016). Student Centric Learning through Planned Hardwork - An Innovative Model. International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), 1(1), 886-898. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61830>.